

Implicit Bias and Bias Cleanse

Implicit Bias Test Instructions

We ask you to choose any of the implicit bias tests as offered by [Project Implicit](#).

You will be directed to a disclaimer which you will need to accept in order to proceed.

Once you are within the test area, you would see many different tests. Each test for a different kind of bias and some explain that most respondents show a particular type of preference. You are free to choose any test from these ones, but we recommend testing an area in which you believe you will not have any biases. If you have time, you could complete a second test in an area in which you will believe you will have biases.

You do not have to share your results with the participants or instructors unless you choose to do so. We will talk about these tests during the Equity, Diversity, and Inclusion Matters; session 2.

If you have any problems or questions, please contact: (barbara.bordalejo@usask.ca).

Optional Bias Cleanse

If you would like to take a more active role in looking at your biases you can try [Look Different](#), a bias cleanse that points your attention towards areas you might not have considered. *Look Different* is the result of a collaboration between the Kirwan Institute and MTV. *Look Different* requires a seven day commitment and, although only a few minutes are required, it demands more than completing the Project Implicit tests. Please feel free to dedicate more or less time to these activities depending on the demands on your schedule.

Implicit Bias Test: Session Two: Optional Exercise

Credit and Attribution:

If you use our exercise, please let us know, and please cite this as Bordalejo, B., Page, A., Kilcer, E. (2020). Implicit Bias and Bias Cleanse.

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